

PREVALENCE OF WORK-RELATED MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS AMONG WEAVERS OF LOOM FACTORIES OF FAISALABAD- A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY

Dr Javeria Ameer¹, Dr Maryam Safdar², Dr Sibgha Zafar³, Dr Humaira Saif⁴, Dr Ayesha⁵
Dr Mubara Nadeem⁶

^{1,3,4,5,6}House officers at Madina Teaching Hospital, Faisalabad,

²Assistant Professor at Department of Rehabilitation Science, The University of Faisalabad, Pakistan

¹drjaveriaameer@gmail.com, ²maryamsafdar.dpt@tuf.edu.pk, ³sibghazafarjs@gmail.com,
⁴humairasaif45@gmail.com, ⁵ayeshaanwarulhaq12@gmail.com, ⁶mubaratalha7@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Dr Maryam Safdar

Abstract

Background: Loom factories are one of the oldest factories in Pakistan, where a considerable number of rural people are engaged in weaving. Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders are major problems associated with demanding working in awkward posture, repetitive extremity movements, different environmental conditions and prolonged working hours that interfere with working ability of weavers.

Methods: This study was conducted on 190 male workers (age range 20-50 years), was working more than 1 year and ≥ 8 hour/day after taking the informed consent. A Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire was used to collect the data and SPSS version 20 was used for data analysis. **Results:** The annual prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders in weavers was higher in shoulder region (42.1%) in neck (40.0%), wrist/hand (33.7%), elbow (30.0%), lower back (29.5%), ankle/feet (23.3%), upper back (20.0%), knee (11.1%) and least was in hip/thigh was (7.4 %). The 1week prevalence of WRMSDs in weavers was higher in neck region (40.0%), shoulder (30.5%), lower back (26.5%), ankle/feet (21.6%), elbow (14.2%), wrist/hand (13.7%) knees (10.5%) and least in hip/thigh (6.8%).

Conclusion: It concluded that the frequency of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders was developing among weavers was higher in shoulder and neck region and least was in hip/thigh because of prolonged working hours, using inappropriate biomechanics.

INTRODUCTION

One of the key industries that significantly contributes to Pakistan's economy is the loom factories. It needs a high repetition at work, which strains the musculoskeletal system and raises the risk of tiredness and insufficient tissue regeneration time, which results in pain and

discomfort (1). In loom workers, the risk and nature of injury is determined by how much time spent at work place and nature of work. Harmful chemicals, high temperature, hazardous machinery, noise, dirt, and mental stress are among the health dangers linked to the

workplace. These factors can lead to occupational diseases and exacerbate pre-existing health issues (2). The term "Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders" (WRMSDs) refers to an excruciating or incapacitating damage to the muscles, ligaments, or nerves brought on by, and made worse by exertion. WMSDs causes both inflammatory and degenerative conditions (tenosynovitis), nerve compression conditions (carpel tunnel syndrome) and conditions that pathology are not known like myalgia and low back pain (3). Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders is developed with the passage of time may be chronic, episodic and condition progress from mild to moderate. The main reason of disabilities, reduced body function, decrease working abilities and decrease quality of life (4). Musculoskeletal Disorders are group of disorders that are neglected in low-middle income countries (LMICs). Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders are considered to be among the most expensive occupational illnesses because to their negative effects on employees productivity and well-being at work. Musculoskeletal Disorders constitute a significant contributor to morbidity and have become the main source of occupational sickness, injury, and disability in many nations (5). The first signal is pain that recover with rest. The earlier recognition of symptoms make it easy to prevent its progression, otherwise disease progresses and become irreversible (6). Co-morbidity among the weavers was high and workers with raised co-morbidity (pain in two or more regions) stated severe pain. According to research body region that are most commonly involved show prevalence of shoulder (76.1%), low back (64.2%), neck (56.3%), and upper back (0.2%) among weavers (15). In a study of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders, between weavers of handloom textile of West Bengal state in India, most dominant body portion were the lower back (68%), followed by arm (49.7%), upper back (44%), knee (38%), shoulder (39.4%), wrist (35.4%) and neck (35.4%). Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders are associated with variety of factors that have positive effect on body region are gender, age, duration of working hour,

workplace and Body Mass Index (BMI) (16). In clinical setting there are few patients who come from loom factories. This is neglected area in occupational injuries. This study emphasis on the prevalence and also demonstrate the complaints of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among loom factory workers because of the lack of awareness related to biomechanics, posture, workplace design, high force activity, repetitive work in the same way and minimum rest time leads them to mental illness that further effect the physical health of loom factories workers. The aim of study is to evaluate the prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders among weavers of loom factories.

METHODOLOGY

It was a cross-sectional study conducted in loom factories of Faisalabad between February 2024 to April 2024, participants were enrolled using purposive sampling. The study population was male weavers (Age range 20-50years) that had work experienced greater than 1 year and working ≥ 8 hours/day were included. Data was collected from total 240 weavers, through face to face interview by using Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire. NMQs consist of two part, first was to be answer by everyone (Q.1 Have you at any time during last 12 months had trouble (such as ache, pain, discomfort, numbness). Second was to be answered by those who have had trouble (Q.2 Have you at any time during the last 12 months been prevented from doing your normal work (at home or away from home because of trouble) and Q 3. Have you had trouble at any time during the last 7 days?) All the workers were informed about the research project and at the start of questionnaire a written consent were obtained from the participants and before commencement of the study approval was taken from the Institutional Review Board (TUF/IRB/396124). Follow the criteria 190(79.2%) participant were included in the study. Collected data were analyzed by using SPSS version 20.

RESULTS

The total numbers of one hundred-ninety male participants were enrolled in this study. The Mean±S.D age of participant of the study to be 34.76±7.95, ranging from 20-50 years. Majority of participant was (n=18) were of 42 years age. Second most age frequency (n=12) was 24 years of age. Least number of common age was (n=1) was 20 years. The Frequency Distribution of Annual and 1 Week prevalence show that the highest prevalence of WRMSDs was found for shoulder pain having annual prevalence rate of (42.1%) followed by neck pain, elbow pain but

less common in hips/thigh pain (7.4%) and weekly prevalence rate of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders was highest in neck pain (31.6%) followed by shoulder pain, lower back pain but less common in hips/thigh pain (6.8%). Neck pain prevented 60 (31.6%) participants from carrying out ADLs in last twelve months. Least pain in Hip/thigh region was prevented 13 (6.8%) participants from carrying out activities of daily livings in last twelve months.

TABLE I: Frequency Distribution of Annual and 1 Week Prevalence

Body Area	12 Months Prevalence		7 Days Prevalence	
	Frequency	Percent%	Frequency	Percent%
Neck	76	40.0	60	31.6
Shoulder	80	42.1	58	30.5
Elbow	57	30.0	27	14.2
Wrists/Hands	64	33.7	26	13.7
Upper Back	38	20.0	23	12.1
Lower Back	56	29.5	50	26.3
Hip/Thigh	14	7.4	13	6.8
Knee	21	11.1	20	10.5
Ankle/Feet	44	23.2	41	21.6

Figure I: Frequency Distribution of Annual and 1 Week Prevalence

TABLE II: Frequency distribution show Impact of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders on Activity of Daily living

Body Area	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percent%	Frequency	Percent%
Neck	60	31.6	130	68.4
Shoulder	58	30.5	132	69.5
Elbow	27	14.2	163	85.8
Wrists/Hands	26	13.7	164	86.3
Upper Back	23	12.1	167	87.9
Lower Back	50	26.3	140	73.7
Hip/Thigh	13	6.8	177	93.2
Knee	20	10.5	170	89.5
Ankle/Foot	41	21.6	149	78.4

DISCUSSION

The aim of cross-sectional study is to evaluate the prevalence of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WRMSDs) among weavers by using Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ) which was completed in four months. In the current study there was 190 male weavers having age between 20-50 years.

Current study result go in favor of recent study that was done to determine the prevalence of work related musculoskeletal disorders among weavers showed that high prevalence in previous 12 month, were reported by in shoulder region (76.1%), in neck (56%), in low back(64%) (1).

On contrary recent study concluded that the complaint of work-related musculoskeletal disorders are more prevalent in lower back (60.6%), in ankle/feet pain was (59.0%), in knees (58.1%) and in the upper back (54.6%) among weavers in past 12 months. Current study has concluded that the highest prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders in shoulder region (42.1%), in neck region (40%) at twelve months (2). Conversely, recent study revealed that prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders was higher in bilateral wrists (76.5%), bilateral elbows (73.44%) and lumbar region (72%) in previous 7 days (7). Compare to current study in which major pain has reported in previous 7 days were in neck and shoulder region where as recent research do not mention

the prevalence of shoulder pain which is most effected in current study (3). Recent cross-sectional study revealed that 81% workers having work-related musculoskeletal disorders in past 12 months and most affected body areas were upper back, lower back, elbow and wrist/hand. The current study findings has contrary to the above findings as the present study has shown the most afflicted area to be shoulder, neck and elbow the prevalence of 42.1%, 40% and 33.7% so the most painful area are different in two studies (4).

CONCLUSION

Prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal disorders was found to be notably high in the shoulder region then followed by neck region due to prolonged working hour, poor posture and ergonomics, working in standing position major reason for work-related musculoskeletal disorders.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study was approved by the Ethical Review Board of The University of Faisalabad.

PARTICIPANTS' CONSENT

Consent letter was granted from the University. All participants of this study were informed about the objectives and methodology of this research project in detail. Written consent was obtained from all participants at the start.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION
COMPETING INTEREST

MS: Conceptualization

SZ, JA, HS, MN: Data collection, study design, search for resources

SZ, JA: Conceptualization, Analysis and interpretation of the data

MS, SZ, JA: Critical revision of the article for important intellectual content

MS: Final approval and guarantor of the article

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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